

Prakṛti māyē :
Using Virtual Reality to deconstruct insect ecology

A Thesis

Submitted to the
Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Mumbai
for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy

by

Pavan Kumar Kaushik

National Centre for Biological Sciences,
Tata Institute of Fundamental Research
Mumbai
May, 2022